

Formulation and Evaluation of Immediate-Release Telmisartan Tablets

Muneera Himayath Banu^{#1}, Bhavani Boddeda^{*2}

*#School of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies, Institute of Science and Technology,
Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Kakinada-533005, Andhra Pradesh, India.*

***Corresponding Author:**

Bhavani Boddeda

School of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies,

Institute of Science and Technology,

Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University,

Kakinada-533005, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Abstract

To meet pharmaceutical requirements such as stability under varying climatic conditions and adequate solubility for gastrointestinal absorption within pH ranges relevant to the gastrointestinal tract, the study sought to develop solid oral formulations of Telmisartan, an angiotensin II receptor antagonist used for the management of hypertension. The formulations were designed to be easy and affordable to prepare. The tablets underwent extensive evaluation, including weight variation and content uniformity tests, along with in vitro dissolution studies using USP apparatus type II. Various parameters were assessed, including the effects of meglumine concentration and different alkalizers on Telmisartan release rates. Notably, Telmisartan exhibits poor and pH-dependent solubility. The resistance to degradation of the improved formulations under accelerated conditions has been demonstrated by stability experiments. Micardis (brand name) and the optimized formulation were compared for dissolution profile similarity using the FDA's SUPAC Guide, especially the f2 factor. Overall, the stability and dissolution properties of the manufactured immediate-release Telmisartan tablets were encouraging. These results highlight better medication delivery and patient outcomes and point to the possibility of increased therapeutic effectiveness in the treatment of hypertension.

Keywords- Telmisartan, Immediate release, wet granulation, Comparative Dissolution Profile, Stability studies.

I. Introduction

An immediate-release drug delivery system is also a conventional type of drug delivery system. It is defined as the Immediate release of special rate-controlling features such as special coatings and other techniques. These preparations are primarily intended to achieve faster onset of action for drugs such as analgesics, antipyretics, and coronary vasodilators. Other advantages include enhanced oral bioavailability [1].

By inhibiting the hormone angiotensin, which relaxes and widens blood vessels, Telmisartan is used to treat hypertension. By lowering high blood pressure, this activity reduces the risk of heart attacks, strokes, and renal problems. As an Angiotensin Receptor Blocker (ARB), Telmisartan has the longest half-life of any ARB, up to 24 hours, and a significant affinity for angiotensin II type 1 (AT1) receptors [2]. While primarily indicated for hypertension treatment, Telmisartan's dual mechanism of action also offers protective benefits against vascular and renal damage associated with diabetes and cardiovascular disease (CVD). Despite its practical insolubility in water and within the pH range of 3 to 9, Telmisartan demonstrates Numerous studies have focused on enhancing the dissolution kinetics of poorly soluble drugs to improve their bioavailability [3].

Adjusting pH in dosage forms has been identified as another promising method to modify the release rate of pH-dependent and ionizable drugs. For instance, incorporating pH modifiers into mini tablets can maintain elevated pH levels, thereby improving the release of drugs like 8-prenylningerin, which are weakly acidic and poorly soluble [4].

In this context, Telmisartan (IR) immediate-release tablets were developed using NaOH and meglumine to elucidate their release behaviors. NaOH, a strong base, facilitates drug dissolution as Telmisartan is soluble in strong bases. Meglumine, acting as a basic agent, also aids in achieving the desired solubility of the formulation. These strategies aim to optimize Telmisartan's dissolution characteristics, potentially improving its bioavailability and therapeutic effectiveness in managing hypertension with minimal side effects [5]- [8].

It's important to note that Telmisartan is supplied in its free acid form and is known for its very poor solubility, which significantly impacts its bioavailability. The drug's solubility is pH-dependent due to its ionizable nature, underscoring the relevance of pH modulation in formulating effective dosage forms. Limited solubility in strong acids (except hydrochloric acid) and increased solubility in strong bases [9].

II. Materials and Methods

A. Materials

Hetero Laboratories in Hyderabad provided the telmisartan, mannitol, meglumine, sodium hydroxide, and magnesium stearate. Every solvent and reagent used complied with pharmacopoeial standards and analytical grade standards.

B. Methods

1) Preformulation studies:

Organoleptic characteristics: A minimal amount of the API is utilized to assess the API's taste and odor, and the API's color and type are ascertained [10].

Solubility: Different buffer solutions with varying pH values (1.2 – 8.0) are used in these investigations.

Melting point: A melting point equipment was used to ascertain it.

Determination of particle size: The size and range of particles were ascertained using a mechanical shaker.

Flow properties: The API and formed granules' flow parameters (angle of repose, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and bulk density) are ascertained.

2) Analytical methods:

Construction of the Telmisartan calibration curve: pH 7.5 phosphate buffer was used to create the calibration curve.

Making a pH 7.5 Phosphate Buffer Solution

6.8 grams of monobasic potassium phosphate and 1.6 grams of sodium hydroxide should be dissolved in 900 milliliters of water. The pH should then be adjusted with 1 N sodium hydroxide to 7.5 and the mixture should be diluted with water to make one liter [11].

Making 0.1N NaOH buffer Solution

In one thousand milliliters of water, dissolve four grams of sodium hydroxide [12].

Studies on Drug-Excipient Compatibility:

Through direct observation

Through FTIR research

C. Preparing tablets of Telmisartan IR:

Mannitol and meglumine pass through mesh #40 combined. Now pass Telmisartan via mesh #20 along with the previously passed meglumine and mannitol.

Dry mixing:

Place the ingredients that have been sifted into the Rapid mixer granulator.

Granulation liquid preparation:

Taken Purified water in a SS vessel equipped with a propeller stirrer and stirred to form a vortex without drawing air into the liquid. Now add Sodium hydroxide slowly while slitting. Stirring was continued to get a clear solution.

Granulation:

Granulated the dry mix by adding sodium hydroxide solution over 2 minutes with Impeller at slow speed and chopper off. Based on granulation consistency, added quantity of purified water over 2 minutes with Impeller at a fast speed and chopper off. Kneaded the wet mass over 2 minutes with Impeller at a fast speed and chopper at a slow speed and checked for complete formation of granules. Discharged the wet mass while mixing with Impeller at a slow speed and chopper off.

Wet milling and drying:

Milled the wet mass by using multi mill fitted with a 12.0 mm screen at a fast speed and knives forward direction Dried the milled wet mass at bed temperature of $55\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a fluid bed dryer and Loss on drying (LOD) was observed at 80°C by using auto mode suitable moisture analyzer.

Milling and drying:

Milled the dried granules using multi mill fitted with a 2.0 mm screen at fast speed and knives forward direction and Loss on drying (LOD) was checked at 80°C by using auto mode suitable moisture analyzer.

Dried the milled granules at bed temperature of $55\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a fluid bed dryer and Loss on drying (LOD) was observed at 80°C by using auto mode suitable moisture analyzer.

Sifting and milling:

The dried granules were sifted through mesh number 24. The retentions were then milled through mesh number 24 using a multi-mill equipped with a 1.0 mm screen at a high speed and blades in a forward direction. The loss on drying (LOD) was determined using an appropriate moisture analyzer in auto mode.

Compression and lubrication:

#60 mesh was used to filter magnesium stearate. Place the sifted magnesium stearate and the dry granules in a blender; process for 5 minutes at 10 rpm. The final combination for tablet compression is compressed into tablets using an appropriate rotary tablet press. Telmisartan (80 mg) is included in the goal weight of 480 mg.

Table I - Formulation Table of Telmisartan IR Tablets

Materials (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
<i>Dry mix:</i>						
Telmisartan	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00	80.00
Meglumine	-	-	-	-	20.00	24.00
Mannitol	387.00	387.00	335.00	381.00	360.00	355.28
<i>Granulation:</i>						
Sodium hydroxide	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	6.720
Purified water	40.00	40.00	42.00	42.00	43.00	51.00
<i>Pre lubrication:</i>						
Mannitol	-	-	50.00	-	-	-
<i>Lubrication:</i>						
Magnesium stearate	8.00	8.00	10.00	14.00	14.00	14.00

D. Evaluation of tablets:

- 1) *Physical appearance*: The outside look should be refined and uniform in size, weight, and appearance.
- 2) *Thickness*: Vernier calipers are used to measure thickness. Five tablets are taken randomly and measured; the average of the results should be taken.
- 3) *Weight variance*: A total of 10 tablets were randomly selected and weighed individually. We compared each person's weight to the average weight to determine the weight variation. Next, the IP limit was compared with the resultant percentage deviation.
- 4) *Hardness*: It is determined by employing a hardness tester. Five tablets are taken randomly and measured; the average of the results should be taken.
- 5) *Disintegration time*: The device uses six glass tubes measuring 7.75 cm x 2.15 mm and is equipped with a 10-mesh screen at the bottom. In an environment of 900 cm³ maintained at 37 °C, the basket is raised and lowered 28-32 times per minute. Each tube contained one tablet and the disintegration time of each tablet was calculated by timing each tablet fragment intact through a number 10 sieve.
- 6) *Friability*: The Roche Fraibilator was used to determine how friable the tablet was. The friability chamber holds 10 carefully weighted tablets that are dropped across a 6-inch and allowed to rotate at 25 rpm for 4 minutes. Four minutes were needed to complete 100 rotations, following which the tablets were weighed again.
- 7) *Drug content*: Tablets were crushed, powder equivalent to 50 mg was taken and dissolved in pH 7.5 phosphate buffer and made up 100 ml in a volumetric flask. Absorbance was measured at 290.5 nm with pH 7.5 phosphate buffer as blank and drug content was calculated.
- 8) *FTIR*: The IR spectral of Telmisartan was observed by preparing a potassium bromide disk. Finally ground Telmisartan powder was mixed with potassium bromide and pressed with specific hydraulic compression. The prepared KBr pellet was then observed under FTIR and the spectrum was recorded. The FTIR spectrum obtained was compared with the spectrum obtained with Telmisartan given.
- 9) *In vitro drug release studies*: Telmisartan tablets (80 mg) were exposed for 45 minutes in phosphate buffer (intestinal fluid pH 7.5) by the USP II paddle method (75 rpm, 37 °C, and 900 ml dissolution medium) with a TDT-06P Tablet dissolution tester (Electro lab). Samples were then taken out of the dissolution medium at predetermined intervals (5, 10, 20, 30, and 45 min), and the drug concentration was determined by UV (Shimadzu) at 290.5 nm. An equivalent amount of fresh medium was added to maintain a constant dissolution volume.

E. Release kinetics:

To determine the mechanism of drug release from tablets, data from *in vitro* release tests were fitted to a variety of kinetics equations, including the zero-order, first-order, Korsmeyer peppas, and Higuchi models. Additionally, the rate constants for each model were calculated [13].

F. Similarity Factor and Dissimilarity Factor Calculation:

There are several methods for dissolution profile comparison. f_2 is the simplest among those methods. Moore &

Flanner proposed a model-independent mathematical approach to compare the dissolution profile using two factors f_1 & f_2 [14].

$$f_1 = \left\{ \left[\sum_{t=1}^n |R_t - T_t| \right] / \left[\sum_{t=1}^n R_t \right] \right\} \cdot 100$$

$$f_2 = 50 \cdot \log \left\{ \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (R_t - T_t)^2 \right) \right]^{-0.5} \cdot 100 \right\}$$

III. Results

- 1) *Organoleptic Properties*: The color was found to be white, Bitter taste & foul odor
- 2) *Solubility*: Solubility studies of Telmisartan were carried out over the pH range of 1.2 – 8.0

Table II - Solubility of The Telmisartan API

S.No.	Medium	Approximate PH	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	0.1N HCl	1.2	1.57478 ± 0.012
2	0.01N HCl	0.01	0.13574 ± 0.014
3	pH 4.5 Acetate Buffer	4.5	0.00026 ± 0.022
4	pH 6.8 Phosphate Buffer	6.8	0.00158 ± 0.052
5	pH 7.5 Phosphate Buffer	7.5	0.00627 ± 0.01
6	pH 8.0 Borate Buffer	8.0	0.01692 ± 0.04
7	Purified water	6.02	0.00030 ± 0.03

- 3) *Melting Point*: The melting point of Telmisartan was found to be 263°C.
- 4) *Flow Properties of API and formulated granules*:

Table III - Flow Properties of the Telmisartan API and Formulated Granules.

API & Formulation	Bulk Density (g/ml)	Tapped Density (g/ml)	Angle of Repose (θ)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
API	0.496 ± 0.04	0.749 ± 0.05	57.86 ± 0.01	33.778 ± 0.02	1.510 ± 0.03
F2	0.504 ± 0.02	0.631 ± 0.06	25.78 ± 0.07	20.849 ± 0.06	1.218 ± 0.06
F3	0.553 ± 0.01	0.604 ± 0.04	30.68 ± 0.09	11.745 ± 0.04	1.251 ± 0.02
F4	0.541 ± 0.05	0.613 ± 0.08	34.74 ± 0.06	12.574 ± 0.07	1.133 ± 0.04
F5	0.519 ± 0.06	0.629 ± 0.09	34.81 ± 0.03	15.754 ± 0.09	1.211 ± 0.07
F6	0.501 ± 0.07	0.630 ± 0.20	33.53 ± 0.02	20.564 ± 0.08	1.257 ± 0.06

- 5) *Determination of Particle Size Distribution of Telmisartan Granules*:

Table IV - Particle Size of Telmisartan Granules

Sieve No.	Empty sieve (gm)	Sample sieve (gm)	Difference (gm)	%Retained	%Cumulative Retained
#30	383.8 ± 0.04	383.9 ± 0.05	0.1 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 0.07	0.4 ± 0.04
#40	367 ± 0.08	367.2 ± 0.06	0.2 ± 0.05	0.8 ± 0.02	1.2 ± 0.06
#60	332.1 ± 0.06	332.6 ± 0.02	0.5 ± 0.07	2 ± 0.06	3.2 ± 0.03
#80	348 ± 0.07	349.3 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.02	5.2 ± 0.04	8.4 ± 0.05
#100	338.6 ± 0.06	340.8 ± 0.05	2.2 ± 0.06	8.8 ± 0.03	17.2 ± 0.03

#200	325.2 ± 0.04	330.7 ± 0.04	5.5 ± 0.02	22 ± 0.02	39.2 ± 0.04
Fine collector	497.4 ± 0.03	512.5 ± 0.07	15.1 ± 0.04	60.4 ± 0.08	99.6 ± 0.05

6) *Loss on Drying:*

Table V - Loss on Drying of Telmisartan Granules

Formulations	Loss On Drying (%)
F1	1.14 ± 0.06
F2	0.45 ± 0.05
F3	0.56 ± 0.03
F4	0.41 ± 0.04
F5	0.68 ± 0.05
F6	0.62 ± 0.01

7) *Standard calibration curve of telmisartan:*Table VI - Absorbance for Standard Graph of Telmisartan with PH 7.5 Phosphate Buffer at λ_{\max} 290.5 nm

S.NO	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	00	0.0000 ± 0.02
2	02	0.1617 ± 0.04
3	04	0.3061 ± 0.06
4	06	0.4653 ± 0.07
5	08	0.5849 ± 0.02
6	10	0.7302 ± 0.04
7	12	0.8292 ± 0.05

Fig. 1. Calibration Curve of Telmisartan

8) *Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies by FTIR*

The probability/possibility of drug excipient interaction was studied by Infrared Spectroscopy using the KBr

pellet method.

The Infrared Spectra of the Pure drug Telmisartan and prepared formulation show a characteristic peak at different frequencies which are as follows.

Table VII - Interpretation of Pure Drug Telmisartan and Optimized Formulation by FTIR

S.No	Functional group	Pure drug Telmisartan Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Optimized formulation Wave number (cm ⁻¹)
1.	C=O (stretching)	1667.24cm ⁻¹	1661.73 cm ⁻¹
2.	C=N (stretching)	1422.64 cm ⁻¹	1438.25 cm ⁻¹
3.	C-H (stretching)	2957.79cm ⁻¹	2976.52 cm ⁻¹
4.	C=C (stretching)	1582.76 cm ⁻¹	-

When the peaks of the formulation spectra were compared with the peak of Telmisartan Pure Drug Spectra, the characteristic peak of Pure Drug were retained indicating the intactness of the drug in the formulation prepared.

Fig. 2. FTIR Graph of Telmisartan API

Fig. 3. FTIR Graph of formulation F6

9) *Physical Parameters:*

The tablets were evaluated for hardness, friability, and weight variation and the results were given in the table.

TABLE VIII - Compression Parameters of Telmisartan IR Tablets

Formulations	Hardness(kp)	Thickness(mm)	Friability (%)	Average weight (mg)
F1	-	-	-	-
F2	13.6 ± 0.04	5.10 ± 0.01	0.003% ± 0.07	479 ± 0.06
F3	13.2 ± 0.05	5.12 ± 0.05	0.009% ± 0.04	484 ± 0.04
F4	13.6 ± 0.09	5.10 ± 0.04	0.100% ± 0.06	477 ± 0.03
F5	13.0 ± 0.03	5.21 ± 0.08	0.006% ± 0.05	481 ± 0.04
F6	12.7 ± 0.05	5.40 ± 0.07	0.004% ± 0.04	480 ± 0.05

10) *Assay:*

Table IX - Assay Results of Telmisartan IR Tablets

Formulation	Assay (%)
F1	-
F2	99.6 ± 0.09
F3	99.9 ± 0.05
F4	100.6 ± 0.06
F5	100.1 ± 0.04
F6	99.9 ± 0.01

11) *Dissolution Data of Innovator and Formulations:*

The following table shows the dissolution data of the innovator MICARDIS® manufactured by Boehringer Ingelheim and the prepared Formulations.

Table X - *In Vitro* Drug Release Profile of F2-F6 Formulations and Reference Product

Time(min)	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	Reference
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	49 ± 0.04	40 ± 0.02	38 ± 0.01	50 ± 0.06	54 ± 0.05	41 ± 0.04
10	57 ± 0.03	56 ± 0.05	45 ± 0.04	71 ± 0.02	82 ± 0.03	67 ± 0.05
20	59 ± 0.08	67 ± 0.01	58 ± 0.06	93 ± 0.04	99 ± 0.04	96 ± 0.07
30	62 ± 0.05	79 ± 0.06	69 ± 0.03	94 ± 0.05	100 ± 0.01	98 ± 0.06
45	69 ± 0.09	90 ± 0.08	75 ± 0.07	94 ± 0.03	101 ± 0.04	100 ± 0.03

Fig. 4. comparative dissolution rates of formulations and reference product

Fig. 5. Comparative dissolution rates of F6 and Innovator

12) Similarity Factor and Dissimilarity Factor Calculation:

The similarity factor f2 and its significance are shown in the following table.

Table XI - Similarity Factor F2 and Its Significance

S. No.	Similarity Factor (f2)	Significance
1.	<50	Test and reference profiles are dissimilar
2.	50 -100	Test and reference profiles are similar
3.	100	Test and reference profiles are identical
4.	>100	The equation yields a negative value

13) Drug Release Kinetics:

The following table shows the drug release kinetics for the innovator product.

Table XII - Drug Release Kinetics of Innovator

S.NO.	Time (min)	Q	log t	log Q	\sqrt{t}	100-Q	log(100-Q)
1.	5	41	0.698	1.612	2.236	59	1.770
2.	10	67	1.000	1.826	3.162	33	1.518
3.	20	96	1.301	1.982	4.472	04	0.602
4.	30	98	1.477	1.991	5.477	02	0.301
5.	45	100	1.653	2.000	6.708	00	0.000

The following table shows the drug release kinetics for the F6 trail.

Table XIII - Drug Release Kinetics of F6 Trail

S.NO.	Time (min)	Q	log t	log Q	\sqrt{t}	100-Q	log(100-Q)
1.	5	48	0.698	1.681	2.236	52	1.716
2.	10	74	1.000	1.869	3.162	26	1.414
3.	20	97	1.301	1.995	4.472	03	0.477
4.	30	98	1.477	2.000	5.477	02	0.301
5.	45	101	1.653	2.004	6.708	-1	0.000

Fig. 6. Zero Order Plot for F6 trail

Fig. 7. First Order Plot for F6 trail

Fig. 8. Higuchi plot for F6 trail

Fig. 9. Korsmeyer Peppas plot for F6 trail

14) Stability Studies:

The stability studies were carried out according to ICH guidelines for the optimized formulation i.e. F6. The following table shows the dissolution profile of F6 stored at three conditions in 1st month, 2nd month, and 3rd month samples was found to be similar to that of initial samples.

Table XIV - % Drug Release Values for Stability Sample

Time(min)	Initial	Ist Month	2nd Month	3rd Month
0	0	0	0	0
5	48 ± 0.05	51 ± 0.03	50 ± 0.04	52 ± 0.05
10	74 ± 0.09	76 ± 0.07	72 ± 0.06	74 ± 0.06

20	97 ± 0.07	97 ± 0.06	95 ± 0.07	99 ± 0.03
30	99 ± 0.04	100 ± 0.04	99 ± 0.05	101 ± 0.01
45	101 ± 0.06	101 ± 0.02	100 ± 0.03	101 ± 0.03

Fig. 10. comparative graph of initial and 1st, 2nd, and 3rd month stability samples

IV. Discussions

The objective of the study is to formulate and evaluate Telmisartan Immediate-release tablets with that of innovator products. Solubility studies were carried out using pH 1.2 to 8.0 media and showed more solubility in 1.2 pH HCl Buffer as shown in Table II. The melting point of Telmisartan was found to be 263^oc.

Flow properties of Telmisartan were determined and showed poor flow characteristics and prepared Telmisartan granules show good flow properties due to the addition of diluents and lubricants as shown in Table III. Particle size determination of Telmisartan Granules is shown in Table IV. Loss On Drying was carried out for Telmisartan Granules and was found to be below the specification of 1% ± 0.5% which is shown in Table V. The standard calibration curve was plotted for Telmisartan using 7.5 pH phosphate Buffer showed linearity and followed Beer's Lambert's law which was shown in Table VI and Figure 1. Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies were carried out using the FTIR KBr pellet method. The results were shown in Table VII and spectrums were shown from Figures 2 and 3.

Post-compression parameters were evaluated like Hardness, Thickness, Friability, and Average weight which were found to be within the specified Acceptance criteria, and the results were shown in Table VIII. An assay was performed for F2 to F6 formulations and was found to be within specifications and results are shown in Table IX. Six formulations were prepared, optimizing concentrations of alkalizers and diluents based on the dissolution profile shown in Table II.

As per the reference product characterization, the F1 formula was manufactured by using a wet granulation process. The batch has failed due to overwetting was observed. To overcome the above problem F2 batch was planned by spray-dried Mannitol. Tablet parameters were not good due to sticking & chipping during the compression stage. To overcome the above problem F3 batch was planned by increasing Magnesium stearate concentration from 8.0 mg to 10 mg. Distribution of Mannitol in intra-granular as well as extra-granular portions.

The batch failed due to the tablet's physical parameters were not good due to sticking & chipping during the compression stage. Weight variation of the tablets was observed at the compression stage. An irregular flow was observed from the hopper during the compression stage. To overcome the above problems, the F4 trial was planned by removal of mannitol from the extra granular stage. Magnesium stearate concentration was increased from 10 mg to 14 mg. The dried granules mesh size was changed from mesh #20 to #24. S-7 CRN-coated punches were used. All the physical parameters were found to be satisfactory but the dissolution profile of the test product was observed as on the lower side when compared to that of Innovator shown in Figure 4. To overcome the above problem, an F5 trial was planned with the inclusion of Meglumine in intra granular stage and the Sodium hydroxide quantity was increased from 5.0 mg to 6.0 mg. All the physical parameters were found to be satisfactory but the dissolution profile of the test product was still observed as slightly on the lower side when compared to that of Innovator shown in Figure 4. To overcome the above problem, the F6 trial was planned with an increased quantity of Meglumine from 20 mg to 24 mg and Sodium hydroxide quantity from 6 mg to 6.72 mg.

The results indicated that the finished product formulation F6, fulfilled all the specifications of the physical properties and in-vitro release and is comparable to the innovator product shown in Figure 5. % drug release values of Telmisartan tablets formulations F2-F6 and Innovator were shown in Table X and comparative graphs were shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Similarity and Dissimilarity factor calculations were carried out for Optimized F6 formulation and Innovator formulation. The similarity factor for the optimized formulation is 84.30 and was found to be similar and its significance was shown in Table XI.

The drug release kinetics values of both the innovator and F6 trial are shown in Table XII & Table XIII. Based on these values, a Zero order plot was plotted for F6 formulation, and the R^2 value was found to be 0.6616 shown in Figure 6. The first-order plot was plotted for F6 formulation and the R^2 value was found to be 0.9098 shown in Figure 7. For formulation trial F6, the R^2 value for First-order kinetics was found to be more. Hence the order of drug release was found to be first order.

The Higuchi plot was plotted for F6 formulation to determine the mechanism of drug release and the R^2 value was found to be 0.9335 shown in Figure 8. Based on Higuchi's equation, the value of the regression coefficient for formulation trial F6 is greater than 0.9. The mechanism of drug release was found to be diffusion. Korsmeyer Peppas was plotted for F6 formulation to determine the mechanism of drug release and the R^2 value was found to be 0.8519 for F6 formulation shown in Figure 9. Based on the Korsmeyer Peppas plot the n value is greater than 0.89. Hence it follows super case-II transport.

The stability studies were carried out according to ICH guidelines for the optimized formulation i.e. F6 and Table XIV shows the dissolution profile of F6 stored at three conditions in the 1st Month, 2nd Month, and 3rd Month and their dissolution profiles are shown in Figure 10. There is no significant change in the dissolution profile and other parameters of the optimized formulation F6 and were found to be within acceptable limits.

V. Conclusion

The findings demonstrate that API worked well with every chosen excipient. The choice of pH 7.5 phosphate buffer over pH 1.2 HCl buffer for the dissolution of telmisartan immediate-release tablets is primarily driven by physiological relevance and the specific properties of telmisartan. Telmisartan is absorbed predominantly in the small intestine, where the pH ranges from approximately 6 to 7.5. pH 7.5 phosphate buffer better mimics the

intestinal pH conditions where telmisartan is solubilized and absorbed. Therefore, using a pH 7.5 buffer provides dissolution conditions that are more relevant to predicting how the drug will behave in vivo. The formulation of Telmisartan IR tablets has been found to have a favorable release profile for up to one hour, as well as sufficient solubility of Telmisartan in the slightly acidic and neutral pH range. Using reasonable doses of NaOH and Meglumine reduces the frequency of dosage administration, minimizes nocturnal episodes, and enhances patient compliance.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the School of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies Institute of Science and Technology JNTUK for the facilitating during this work.

References

- [1] KD Tripathi, "Essentials of Medical Pharmacology" - Eight edition - 2019.
- [2] Remington, "The Science and Practice of Pharmacy", 23rd Edition, pg.no.333
- [3] Chien Y. W., "Novel Drug Delivery System" (II ndEdn), Revised and expanded, 1992; pg.no: 139- 40.
- [4] www.ich.org - ICH Official website.
- [5] Lee V.H., Robinson J.R. in, "Sustained and Controlled Release Drug Delivery System" Marcel Dekker, New York, pg. no. 71-121., 138-71.
- [6] Bremecker KD, Seidel K, Böhner A. Polyacrylate gels: use of new bases in drug formulation [in German]. *Dtsch Apoth Ztg* 1990; 130(8): 401–403.
- [7] Chromy V, Kulhanek V, Fischer J. D-(–)-N-Methylglucamine buffer for pH 8.5 to 10.5. *Clin Chem* 1978; 24(2): 379–381.
- [8] Chromy V, Zahradnicek L, Voznicek J. Use of N-Methyl-D-glucamine as a buffer in the determination of serum alkaline phosphatase activity. *Clin Chem* 1981; 27(10): 1729–1732.
- [9] Japan Pharmaceutical Excipients Council. Japanese Pharmaceutical Excipients Directory 1996. Tokyo: Yakuji Nippon, 1996: 305.
- [10] Allen LV. Featured excipient: capsule and tablet diluents. *Int J Pharm Compound* 2000; 4(4): 306–310, 324–325.
- [11] Yoshinari T, Forbes RT, York P, Kawashima Y. Improved compaction properties of mannitol after a moisture-induced polymorphic transition. *Int J Pharm* 2003; 258(1–2): 121–131.
- [12] Kanig JL. Properties of fused mannitol in compressed tablets. *J Pharm Sci* 1964; 53: 188–192.
- [13] Ward DR, Lathrop LB, Lynch MJ. Dissolution and compatibility considerations for the use of mannitol in solid dosage forms. *J Pharm Sci* 1969; 58: 1464–1467.
- [14] Ghanem AH, Sakr FM, Abdel-Ghany G. Mechanical and physical properties of sulfamethoxazole-mannitol solid dispersion in tablet form. *Acta Pharm Fenn* 1986; 95: 167–172.